

In-depth modelling of tree and crop water relations in agroforestry

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Context

Climate change poses an increasingly severe threat to global agricultural systems (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (IPCC), 2022), with direct implications for food security across multiple dimensions (Christian et al., 2023; Lian et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2023). Among the most critical consequences of ongoing climate change is the intensification and growing frequency of extreme climatic events, particularly heat waves and flash droughts (Gebrechorkos et al., 2025; Otkin et al., 2018). Under conditions of severe water deficit, plants face the risk of hydraulic failure: declining water potentials drive xylem cavitation, leading to embolism formation, irreversible tissue damage, and ultimately significant yield losses [Brodribb et al.; Choat et al.; Tyree et al.]. Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) appears to be especially vulnerable to cavitation-induced hydraulic dysfunction during its reproductive stages (Harrison Day et al., 2024, 2023; Harrison Day and Brodribb, 2023), making the protection of its hydraulic integrity a matter of direct relevance to global food security. Plant water potential (Ψ_{plant}) constitutes the primary determinant of cavitation onset and is therefore a key physiological variable to monitor and model in the context of drought stress (De Swaef et al., 2022).

Agroforestry systems (AFS) have been identified by the IPCC and FAO (FAO, 2023) as one of the priority adaptation strategies in the face of climate change. By integrating trees within cropped areas, AFS generate a distinctive microclimate characterized by partial shading, reduced wind speed, and modified humidity regimes. That could theoretically buffer the water stress experienced by intercropped plants and, by extension, reduce their exposure to cavitation risk. However, this hypothesis has not yet been rigorously evaluated through a hydraulic or cavitation lens. A critical complication lies in the fact that two competing mechanisms, which are rarely disentangled in the literature, operate simultaneously in AFS. On the one hand, shading may improve the crop water balance by reducing evapotranspiration demand. On the other hand, belowground root competition for water between trees and wheat may partially or entirely offset this benefit, or even reverse it under certain conditions (Cardinael et al., 2020, 2015; Nair et al., 2021). The net hydraulic outcome for wheat in an agroforestry context therefore remains an open question.

Assessing the full range of agroforestry effects under current and future climate scenarios is logistically challenging to achieve through field experimentation alone, which has motivated the development of agroforestry models (AFM) such as APSIM, Hi-sAFe, and WANULCAS. These frameworks typically combine a crop growth model (CGM) for the intercrop component with a module representing tree growth and resource competition. Yet existing AFMs remain limited in their representation of fine ecophysiological traits. This reflects a persistent disciplinary divide between agronomy and ecophysiology: agroforestry agronomists tend to measure yield, photosynthetically active radiation, and soil moisture, while ecophysiologicalists focus on leaf water potential, hydraulic conductance, and embolism, traits that are absent from current AFS models. Plant water potential represents precisely the missing disciplinary bridge between these two communities, linking the microclimatic variables routinely measured by agronomists to the cavitation processes studied by ecophysiologicalists (De Swaef et al., 2022). Moreover, existing models implicitly assume that shading confers a net benefit to the crop water balance, while spatial belowground water competition is rarely accounted for, potentially leading to a systematic overestimation of the hydraulic benefit of tree cover.

Goals

The present is a first approach, a proof of concept, by investigating whether the microclimatic interactions and belowground water competition characteristic of agroforestry systems create conditions that alleviate hydraulic stress and reduce cavitation risk in intercropped wheat, or whether, conversely, root water competition and shading-induced physiological trade-offs act as aggravating factors under drought conditions.

Materials & Methods

Materials

In order to model the reaction of an agroforestry system, two models will be used. The Hi-sAFe model in order to represent the agroforestry systems at plot level. The SUREAU model in order to represent the fine hydraulics processes happening at the plant level of the intermediate crop of the systems.

Hi-sAFe is a mechanistic, biophysical model designed to simulate tree-crop interactions in agroforestry systems. It couples the STICS crop model to a dedicated tree module that incorporates plasticity mechanisms responding to competition for light, water, and nitrogen. Its three-dimensional and spatially explicit structure allows it to represent competition and facilitation processes with a spatial resolution that one-dimensional models cannot achieve. The model can be used to explore agroforestry designs (tree spacing, row orientation, crop type), management strategies (pruning,

Figure 1: "The simulated Hi-sAFe scene reduces a landscape into its simplest replicable unit and is discretized into a 3D, spatially explicit voxel grid. Periodic boundary conditions (PBC) allow for the scene to be repeated infinitely in all directions." Taken from (Dupraz et al., 2019)

thinning, irrigation, fertilization), and responses to environmental variation such as climate change scenarios, soil depth, or soil fertility (Figure 1).

SUREAU is a process-based mechanistic model that predicts the risk of xylem hydraulic failure under drought. Its core is the hydraulic and hydric functioning of the plant, representing both water flows and water storage pools through variable hydraulic conductance across plant organs described by their symplasmic and apoplasmic compartments. It operates by segmenting the soil-plant-atmosphere continuum into compartments, with water fluxes between segments determined by water potential gradients. The model can be combined with simplified photosynthesis, energy budget, and growth modules, though its primary function remains hydraulic. It is parameterized using ecophysiological

traits such as vulnerability curves (P50, S50), stomatal regulation thresholds, and leaf water potential, making it particularly well suited to track cavitation risk under water stress scenarios.

Methods

Chaining Approach

The modelling framework is based on a soft-chaining approach in which the outputs of the agroforestry model serve as inputs for the plant hydraulic model. This methodology is described in detail in [REF FIRST ARTICLE].

Climatic Scenario

Heatwave events are represented through direct modification of the climatic dataset prior to any model simulation. Temperature forcing is applied from a defined start date over a specified duration, according to the parameters summarized in [Table X].

Agroforestry Plot Configuration

Crop and Cultivar

Bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was selected as the intercrop species, owing to its economic relevance and the abundance of published data available for model parameterization. The wheat cultivar chosen for this study is Rubisko, whose key agronomic parameters are reported in [Table X]. The technical operations applied to the plot are summarized in [Table X].

Tree Species

The tree component of the agroforestry system is black walnut (*Juglans nigra* L.), selected for its prominence in Western European agroforestry systems and for being among the best-parameterized species available in Hi-sAFe. Key tree parameters used in the model are listed in [Table X].

Experimental Design

The study aims to characterize the dynamics of light and water resource competition within an agroforestry system. Since tree development constitutes the primary driver of both above- and belowground competition, the experimental design focuses on how tree age and stand density jointly influence these competitive processes. Tree dimensions directly determine the extent of canopy shading and root water uptake, both of which can be modelled as a function of tree age and plantation density using Hi-sAFe.

The design therefore consists in simulating tree development across a factorial combination of ages and densities, so as to capture the progressive intensification of resource competition over time. Three plantation densities and four tree ages were considered, yielding twelve simulation modalities:

- Plantation densities: 100, 200, and 400 trees ha⁻¹. The 400 trees ha⁻¹ density allows comparison with Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2018); the 200 trees ha⁻¹ density corresponds to the Restinclières experimental site.
- Tree ages: 5, 15, 25, and 45 years.

For the same reason of economy of computing, not all cells are computed throughout the SUREAU model. Only six cells are conserved in each cells. Those cells are selected to keep the closest and furthest cells from the tree in the scene from each sides of the row (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Schematic of the cells selection in the Hi-sAFé scene

Followed Variables

Chaining Control

The chaining process is evaluated using potential evapotranspiration (PET), actual evapotranspiration (AET), and plant water potential (PWP), following the method described in Soulard et al. (2026).

Plant Hydraulic Response to Drought

The effects of drought on plant hydraulics are assessed using the following variables extracted from SUREAU model outputs:

- Leaf water potential (LWP)
- Leaf evaporation rate (LER)
- Stomatal evaporation rate (SER)
- Percentage loss of conductance at the leaf level (PLC leaf)
- Relative water content of the leaf symplasm (RWC leaf symp)
- Whole-plant stomatal conductance (gs)
- Leaf area (LA)

Light Interception Dynamics

Light interception is characterized at the cell level using photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), decomposed into its direct and diffuse components. In addition to instantaneous values, campaign-integrated PAR metrics are computed and compared across simulation modalities. This must be linked

Figure 3: "Aboveground tree representation in Hi-sAFe. H: tree height (m). Hp: pruned height (m). DBH: trunk diameter at breast height (m). DCB: trunk diameter at the base of the crown (m). rz: vertical crown radius (m, $r_z = (H;H_p)/2$). rx and ry: independent horizontal crown radii. Figure 4. Aboveground tree representation in Hi-sAFe. H: tree height (m). Hp: pruned height (m). DBH: trunk diameter at breast height (m). DCB: trunk diameter at the base of the crown (m). rz: vertical crown radius (m, $r_z = (H;H_p)/2$). rx and ry: independent horizontal crown radii." taken from (Dupraz et al., 2019)

with the dynamics of the dimensions of the tree during the campaign (Figure 3).

Water Availability Dynamics

Soil water dynamics are assessed through the spatial description of both the tree and crop root systems at the cell level, from which water uptake by each component is derived. Three-dimensional representations of available soil water within the scene can also be produced. As for light, campaign-integrated water uptake values are computed and compared against monocrop reference simulations.

Preliminary Results

Plant Hydraulic Response to Drought

Here is the dynamic of the response of the crop to a drought event (Figure 4). Mean leaf evaporation rate (blue) and stomatal evaporation rate (cyan, left axis, $\text{mmol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$) alongside leaf water potential (red, right axis, MPa). Both transpiration fluxes exhibit pronounced diurnal oscillations early in the period, which progressively dampen and collapse to near-zero values by day 183, while leaf water potential declines continuously to below -3 MPa, indicating severe water stress. Leaf relative water content (RWC_Leaf, blue, left axis) and percentage loss of hydraulic conductance (PLC_Leaf, red, right axis, %). RWC decreases steadily from ~ 1.0 to ~ 0.5 , while PLC increases from ~ 0 to $\sim 65\%$, with the two variables intersecting around day 180, marking a critical threshold of hydraulic dysfunction. Stomatal conductance (g_s , blue, left axis, $\text{mmol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$) and leaf area index (green, right axis). High-amplitude diurnal fluctuations in g_s (peaks $>500 \text{ mmol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$) are observed early in the simulation before abruptly declining to near-zero around day 178;179, consistent with near-complete stomatal closure

Figure 4: Temporal dynamics of leaf water status, hydraulic dysfunction, and stomatal regulation simulated by SUREAU during a drought episode simulated with the SUREAU model for a monocrop system.

under severe embolism. Leaf area index declines progressively in a stepwise manner from ~ 4.5 to ~ 0.5 , reflecting cumulative drought-induced leaf senescence.

Light Interception Dynamics

Temporal dynamics of the ratio of photosynthetically active radiation available to the crop in agroforestry relative to open-field conditions ($\text{PAR}_{\text{AF}} / \text{PAR}_{\text{WT}}$, %), simulated across a full growing season (crop age 0;250 days). Results are presented for four tree ages (5, 15, 25, and 45 years; rows) and three stand densities (101, 204, and 400 trees ha^{-1} ; columns) (Figure 5). Each line represents a distinct spatial cell position relative to the tree row, as indicated in the legend. A value of 100% denotes the absence of shading. The vertical dashed line indicates a key phenological stage at approximately day 180. At the youngest tree age (5 years), PAR availability remains near 100% across all densities and spatial positions, reflecting negligible canopy interception. As tree age increases, shading intensifies

progressively, with cumulative PAR ratios declining throughout the season in all configurations. This decline is most pronounced at tree age 45 combined with the highest density (400 trees ha⁻¹), where PAR availability falls below 50% in the most shaded positions by the end of the growing season. Across

Figure 5: Temporal dynamics of cumulative PAR shading in agroforestry as a function of tree age, stand density, and spatial position

all tree ages and densities, marked spatial heterogeneity is observed among cell positions: cells in close proximity to the tree row experience substantially greater radiation attenuation than those located farther away, with the (1/D, 0) cell (cyan) consistently showing the lowest PAR availability. Differences among spatial positions widen with increasing tree age and stand density, reflecting the progressive expansion of tree canopy. These patterns underscore the combined influence of stand structural parameters and intra-plot spatial position on light resource partitioning in agroforestry systems.

Water Availability Dynamics

Temporal dynamics of mean daily water uptake (mm day⁻¹) by the crop (solid lines) and trees (dashed lines) in each soil layer (Figure 6) (Layer 1: green, Layer 2: orange, Layer 3: blue, Layer 4: pink), simulated over one full annual cycle (October 2018 ; October 2019). Results are presented for four tree ages (5, 15, 25, and 45 years; rows) and three stand densities (101, 204, and 400 trees ha⁻¹; columns). Layers in which both actors extract water simultaneously define the temporal competition zone.

Crop water uptake is concentrated in spring (approximately April to June 2019), primarily from the upper soil layers (Layers 1;3), and ceases abruptly following crop maturity and harvest. Tree water uptake exhibits a contrasting phenology: it begins gradually in spring, overlapping temporally with crop uptake in the upper layers, and extends well into summer and early autumn, long after crop water

demand has ceased. This temporal overlap in spring constitutes the main competition window between the two actors.

The relative contribution of trees to total water uptake increases markedly with tree age. At tree age 5, tree uptake is negligible across all layers and densities, with the crop dominating the soil water balance. At tree age 15, tree uptake becomes detectable, primarily from Layer 4, and persists into the post-harvest period. At tree ages 25 and 45, tree uptake from Layer 4 (pink dashed) is substantial, reaching peak values of 2;3 mm day⁻¹, and extends throughout summer, reflecting the progressive deepening of tree root systems and their capacity to exploit water reserves inaccessible to the crop. Stand density has a comparatively modest effect on the overall pattern, though uptake rates in deeper layers tend to be slightly higher at greater densities, consistent with increased tree biomass and root development. These results illustrate a clear ontogenetic shift in belowground resource partitioning, from weak competition at early stand stages to pronounced niche complementarity in depth and time at older tree ages.

Figure 6: Temporal dynamics of soil water uptake by crop and trees across soil layers, tree ages, and stand densities

Effects of Agroforestry on Plant Hydraulic Response to Drought

Temporal dynamics of the daily difference in potential evapotranspiration between open-field (ETP_WT) and agroforestry (ETP_AF) conditions (mm day⁻¹), presented as stacked bar charts over the crop growing season (crop age 70;185 days) (Figure 7). Results are shown for four tree ages (5, 15, 25, and 45 years; rows) and three stand densities (101, 204, and 400 trees ha⁻¹; columns). Each color represents the contribution of a distinct spatial cell position relative to the tree row (see legend). The green background indicates that ETP_WT exceeds ETP_AF (i.e., potential evapotranspiration is lower in the agroforestry plot than in open field), while a red background would indicate the opposite; the

near-exclusive dominance of the green background across all panels confirms that agroforestry systematically reduces the energy available for evapotranspiration relative to open-field conditions throughout the growing season.

At tree age 5, differences are negligible across most densities, with only marginal contributions emerging at the highest density (400 trees ha⁻¹) toward the end of the season, reflecting the limited canopy development of young trees. As tree age increases, ETP differences amplify progressively and consistently across all densities: at tree age 45, daily differences reach up to 1.5;1.75 mm day⁻¹, indicating a substantial attenuation of the evaporative demand experienced by the crop under mature tree canopies. This amplification intensifies over the course of the growing season, consistent with increasing canopy light interception following budburst and leaf area development. Among spatial cell positions, the (1/D, 0) cell (cyan) and the (D, -d) cell (pink) contribute most prominently to the total ETP difference, reflecting their proximity to the tree row and consequently greater exposure to shading. The effect of stand density on the magnitude of ETP differences is moderate compared to the effect of tree age, though higher densities tend to produce more spatially homogeneous reductions across cell positions. These results indicate that tree canopy shading substantially reduces atmospheric

evaporative demand in agroforestry systems, with potential consequences for crop water stress mitigation under drought conditions.

Figure 7: Temporal dynamics of potential evapotranspiration differences between open-field and agroforestry conditions across spatial cell positions, tree ages, and stand densities

Temporal dynamics of the daily difference in actual evapotranspiration between open-field (ETR_WT) and agroforestry (ETR_AF) conditions (mm day^{-1}), presented as stacked bar charts over the crop growing season (crop age 70;185 days) (Figure 8). Results are shown for four tree ages (5, 15, 25, and 45 years; rows) and three stand densities (101, 204, and 400 trees ha^{-1} ; columns). Each color represents the contribution of a distinct spatial cell position relative to the tree row (see legend). The green background indicates that ETR_WT exceeds ETR_AF (open-field crop transpires more than agroforestry crop), while the red background indicates the opposite (ETR_AF exceeds ETR_WT).

In contrast to the uniformly positive pattern observed for potential evapotranspiration ($\text{ETP}_{\text{WT}} - \text{ETP}_{\text{AF}}$), the ETR difference exhibits a more complex temporal structure, reflecting the interplay between atmospheric demand, soil water availability, and stomatal regulation. For the majority of the growing season (crop age 70;~150 days), differences remain close to zero or slightly negative across

most configurations, indicating that actual crop transpiration is marginally higher in agroforestry than in open field during this period. This facilitation effect is most apparent at tree age 5, where negative values persist until late in the season, suggesting that tree shading partially alleviates drought stress and allows the agroforestry crop to sustain higher transpiration rates relative to open-field conditions.

From approximately day 150 onward, a pronounced reversal occurs in all configurations except tree age 5: $ETR_{WT} - ETR_{AF}$ shifts strongly positive, with sharp daily spikes reaching up to 1.5;1.75 mm day⁻¹ near the end of the growing season. This late-season pattern, dominated by the (D, -d) (pink) and (1/D, 0) (cyan) cells, indicates that under drought conditions the open-field crop maintains higher actual transpiration rates than the agroforestry crop during the critical grain-filling period, likely reflecting the combined effects of reduced stomatal conductance and accelerated senescence in the most shaded cells. The magnitude of this late-season positive difference increases with tree age and is relatively consistent across densities, underlining the predominant role of canopy development over stand structure in driving ETR divergence between systems. Together, these results highlight that the net effect of agroforestry on crop water use shifts from facilitation early in the season to increased water limitation late in the season under drought, with implications for yield formation.

Figure 8: Temporal dynamics of actual evapotranspiration differences between open-field and agroforestry conditions across spatial cell positions, tree ages, and stand densities

Discussion & Perspectives

Shading-induced reduction of atmospheric evaporative demand

The systematic reduction of potential evapotranspiration (PET) under tree canopies, observed across all stand configurations and increasingly pronounced with tree age, is consistent with the well-documented microclimate buffering effect of agroforestry systems (Luedeling et al., 2016). The near-exclusive dominance of positive PET differences throughout the growing season confirms that canopy interception fundamentally alters the energy balance of the intercrop environment, attenuating the radiative forcing that drives atmospheric water demand. The progressive amplification of this effect with tree age directly reflects the ontogeny of canopy closure: as trees develop structural biomass and expand their leaf area, they intercept an increasingly large fraction of incoming solar radiation, reducing net radiation and sensible heat flux at the crop surface. The spatial gradient in PET reduction, most pronounced in cells adjacent to the tree row, is mechanistically consistent with the geometric shadowing patterns documented in Hi-sAFe (Dupraz et al., 2019) and confirms that tree-crop spatial configuration is a first-order determinant of the microclimate experienced by the intercrop.

Importantly, however, a reduction in PET does not automatically translate into reduced drought stress. PET quantifies the atmospheric evaporative demand independently of the plant's actual water status. The relationship between PET reduction and hydraulic stress relief is mediated by soil water availability, root architecture, and stomatal regulation, all of which may decouple the two variables under severe drought, as the AET results discussed below illustrate.

Shift from facilitation to competition

The temporal dynamics of actual evapotranspiration (AET) differences reveal a more complex picture than the PET results alone would suggest, and constitute arguably the most ecologically informative output of the present analysis. During the early and mid-season (crop age roughly 70 to 150 days), AET differences are near zero or slightly negative, indicating that crops in agroforestry plots transpire marginally more than their open-field counterparts. This early-season facilitation aligns with the hypothesis that moderate shading buffers vapour pressure deficit and reduces stomatal closure under non-limiting soil water conditions, allowing the intercrop to maintain higher gas exchange rates (Artru et al., 2017; Tsonkova et al., 2012). The effect is most apparent at tree age 5, where root competition is negligible and shading provides a net benefit without countervailing effects from belowground resource depletion.

The reversal that emerges from approximately day 150 onward, where AET differences shift strongly positive and open-field crops sustain higher transpiration than their agroforestry counterparts, represents a critical finding with direct implications for hydraulic integrity during grain filling. This late-season transition is most plausibly explained by the compounded effects of advanced leaf senescence in the most shaded cells, progressive soil water depletion in upper soil layers resulting from tree root competition during the overlapping spring uptake window, and earlier stomatal closure under combined light and water limitation in agroforestry compared to open field. The fact that this reversal intensifies with tree age while remaining relatively insensitive to stand density strongly implicates canopy development, rather than stand structural configuration per se, as the primary driver of late-season divergence between systems.

These findings challenge the implicit assumption embedded in many agroforestry models that tree shading confers a net and continuous benefit to the crop water balance. Instead, the results suggest a temporal trade-off: early facilitation under moderate shade, followed by hydraulic disadvantage during the most sensitive phenological stage.

Belowground competition

The water uptake dynamics across soil layers provide a mechanistic basis for understanding the aboveground hydraulic outcomes described above. The temporal overlap between crop and tree uptake in upper soil layers during spring constitutes a genuine competition window whose intensity scales with tree age and root system development. The progressive shift of tree uptake toward deeper soil layers with advancing tree age reflects the well-documented rooting depth plasticity of *Juglans nigra*, which allocates biomass to deep horizons in response to competition and seasonal water depletion (Cardinael et al., 2015; Nair et al., 2021). While this vertical niche differentiation may superficially suggest complementarity, the simultaneous maintenance of tree uptake from upper layers during the crop growth period means that complementarity remains incomplete, particularly at older tree ages where deep root uptake is substantial but surface competition is not fully alleviated.

The ontogenetic shift documented here, from negligible tree uptake at age 5 to peak daily values of 2 to 3 mm day⁻¹ from deep layers at ages 25 to 45, has direct implications for the long-term trajectory of agroforestry hydraulic dynamics. Young agroforestry systems are likely to exhibit net facilitation on the intercrop water balance, while mature systems may progressively shift toward a competitive regime that counteracts the atmospheric demand buffering provided by canopy shading. This temporal dynamic is rarely captured in short-term field experiments and underscores the value of long-term process-based simulation.

Implications for wheat hydraulic integrity and cavitation risk

The plant-level hydraulic simulations produced by SUREAU under monocrop drought conditions illustrate the cascade of physiological responses that occurs as soil water potential declines: progressive stomatal closure, leaf water potential falling well below -3 MPa, percentage loss of conductance (PLC) approaching 65%, and concurrent leaf area reduction through drought-induced senescence. These dynamics are broadly consistent with published vulnerability thresholds for *Triticum aestivum* (Harrison Day et al., 2023, 2024), where P50 values indicate that substantial xylem embolism can occur at leaf water potentials already reached under moderate drought. The intersection of relative water content and PLC curves near day 180 marks the transition from stomatal to hydraulic regulation, a critical threshold beyond which recovery becomes increasingly costly without rehydration.

Placing this hydraulic vulnerability information within the agroforestry context raises a theoretically tractable but empirically underexplored question: does the PET reduction generated by canopy shading translate into a measurable delay or attenuation of hydraulic failure under drought? The PET results suggest that, in principle, agroforestry could reduce the energy available for evapotranspiration sufficiently to maintain leaf water potential above critical embolism thresholds for longer than open-field conditions would allow. The late-season AET divergence complicates this interpretation, however. Lower AET in agroforestry during grain filling may reflect accelerated hydraulic failure rather than water conservation, particularly in cells where combined light and water limitation is most severe. Distinguishing between protective stomatal regulation and stress-induced dysfunction will require direct comparison of SUREAU outputs across agroforestry and open-field chaining scenarios, which constitutes the logical next step of this analysis.

Limitations and perspectives

Several limitations of the present framework warrant acknowledgment. The soft-chaining approach relies on the assumption that the hydraulic parameterization of wheat derived from monocrop studies remains valid under the modified microclimate of agroforestry. Shading-induced shifts in leaf morphology, stomatal density, and xylem anatomy, documented in other species under canopy

conditions, could alter the vulnerability curve parameters used to drive SUREAU and introduce systematic bias in the hydraulic predictions. In addition, the current analysis is restricted to a single soil type, a single climate year (2018 to 2019), and a single tree row orientation. Sensitivity analyses across soil texture gradients and interannual climate variability would be necessary to assess the generalizability of the ontogenetic and spatial patterns described here. The six-cell spatial subsampling used to reduce computational cost also excludes intermediate positions that may exhibit non-linear shading and competition gradients, potentially underestimating intra-plot spatial heterogeneity.

Future work should explicitly compare SUREAU hydraulic outputs, particularly leaf water potential and PLC, between chained agroforestry and open-field simulations under both ambient and projected SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios. Incorporating heatwave events as climate forcing would allow assessment of the degree to which tree canopies buffer extreme thermal and vapour pressure deficit spikes, and whether this buffering is sufficient to prevent hydraulic failure in wheat during critical phenological windows. The integration of a spatially explicit hydraulic model within an agroforestry simulation framework, as prototyped here, represents a methodological advance that could meaningfully narrow the disciplinary gap between agroforestry agronomy and plant ecophysiology.

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